

**THE PRAGMATIC FUNCTIONS OF THE FRENCH LANGUAGE UNITS USED IN
RUSSIAN LITERARY TEXTS****Khalmuradova Zebiniso Shavkatovna**

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Abstract. The present article demonstrates analysis of pragmatic functions of the French language units used in Russian literary works. Such French borrowings fulfill stylistic, semantic and pragmatic functions and add special melody, beauty and sound to the text. The pragmatic features of linguistic activity, the factors that give rise to these features, is important for determining the social nature of the language. The extracts from original texts are compared with their Uzbek translation version.

Key words: literary personage, French language units, pragmatic meaning, pragmatic functions, stylistic, semantic, linguocultural peculiarities.

The dichotomy of language and speech plays an important role in the development of modern linguistics. This phenomenon attracted the attention of F. Saussure and scientists from various scientific centers of the world. In particular, F. Saussure analyzed the relationship between language and speech in his scientific works within the framework of the following opposing aspects: social / individual, abstract / concrete, passive / active, mental / physical, virtual / real, etc. [Saussure 1977: 57].

According to R. Engler, linguistic activity creates the basis for the activation of language [Engler 1998: 16]. Language serves society, because people create their speech in society with the help of language. Linguistic experience shows that the principles that ensure linguistic activity differ from the principles of other aspects. Although these aspects are related to each other, they act independently.

Various linguistic means are used in works of art to describe human values. It also seems effective to refer to the stylistic features of the literary text, which expands modern ideas about the specific features of the functioning of linguistic units in the literary text and their impact on the reader [Lazareva 2019: 8].

The study of the pragmatic features of linguistic activity, the factors that give rise to these features, is important for determining the social nature of the language. This makes it possible to search for evidence that linguistic communication occurs in accordance with social and linguistic laws. Due to the scope of social experience, communicative situations change, and the pragmatic structure, which was initially a simple structure, changes over time and becomes more complex. Therefore, linguistic analysis should begin with pragmatics [Safarov 2018: 41].

In the analysis of a literary text, attention should be paid not only to the word composition, but also to the pragmatic content of communicative situations.

Indeed, the text of a work of art has intellectual, emotional properties, and therefore affects the reader's consciousness and imagination. A number of pragmatic meanings are presented in the following context: greeting, polite address, congratulations, and positive assessment (compliment):

Bonjour, ma chère, je vous félicite, - сказала гостя. - Quelle délicieuse enfant! - прибавила она, обращаясь к матери [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 36].

In translation version all pragmatic functions are preserved:

Salomatmisiz, azirim, bayramingiz qutlug' bo'lsin, - dedi mehmonxonim, so'ngra qizning onasiga murojaat qildi. - Ajoyib farzand ekan-a! [Tolstoy "Urush va tinchlik", I, II kitoblar: 62].

French words used in novels by Russian writers serve various pragmatic functions. For example, in the following passage, a character expresses his advice to a friend in French:

- *Ah mon ami!* – сказала она с тем же жестом, как утром с сыном, дотрагиваясь до его руки, - *croyez, que je souffre, autant que vous, mais soyez homme. Soyez homme, mon ami, c'est moi qui veillerai à vos intérêts*, - сказала она в ответ на его взгляд и еще скорее пошла по коридору [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 71-72]. The meaning of the text in Uzbek: “Do ‘stim, ishonib, men ham qiynalyapman, ammo siz o‘zingizni erkaklarcha tutishingiz kerak. Siz erkak bo‘lishingiz kerak, men esa manfaatlaringizni qo‘llab-quvvatlayman”. In this context, it is important that the character expresses his speech in French. First, it shows that this is a secret between the character and his friend, and second, it shows the closeness of the relationship between them.

The meaning of disapproval is expressed at different levels in the speech act. For example, in the following example, the meaning of disapproval expressed in French is very strong:

В эту минуту дверь, та страшная дверь, на которую так долго смотрел Пьер и которая так тихо отворялась, быстро с шумом откинулась, стукнув об стену, и средняя княжна выбежала оттуда и вплеснула руками. Что вы делаете! – отчаянно проговорила она, - *Il s'en va et vous me laissez seule* [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 79]. The French phrase serves the pragmatic function of reprimanding, even fighting.

Let's analyze another context:

Mon ami! – сказала мать умоляющим голосом, опять дотрагиваясь до руки сына, как будто это прикосновение могло успокаивать или возбуждать его [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 45].

In the Uzbek version translator changes the words: *mon ami* – instead of the word “do‘stim” is used the word “jigarim”:

Jigarim! – dedi onasi yalingan tovush bilan yana o‘g‘lining qo‘lini ushlab, xuddi bu ushlashi o‘g‘liga tasalli beradigan yoki uning g‘ashiga tegadiganday [Tolstoy “Urush va tinchlik”, I, II kitoblar: 78].

There is another example:

-*Voions, ma bonne* Анна Михайловна, *laissez faire Catiche* [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 78]. From a pragmatic point of view, the idea expressed in French in this passage serves the function of consolation and pacification. The speaker recognizes the object of speech, Katysh, and, although he does not take her side, he is in favor of leaving her alone.

The pragmatic function of asking for forgiveness is realized in the literary text more often with the help of French lexicon:

- *Я знаю, милая, добрая княжна*, - сказала Анна Михайловна, хватаясь рукой за портфель и так крепко, что видно было, она не скоро его пустит. – *Милая княжна, я вас прошу, я вас умоляю, пожалейте его. Je vous en conjure...* [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 78]. The request, made in French, was a sign of the speaker's politeness.

Although the following text uses only one French word, it has a specific pragmatic meaning:

Я знаю, что я всегда буду первою confidente моих дочерей и что Николенька, по своему пылкому характеру, ежели будет шалить (мальчику нельзя без этого), то все не так, как эти петербургские господа [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 39].

The word “confidente” expresses the meaning “maslahatchi”.

The same meaning is saved in translation:

...hamma vaqt qizlarimning birinchi confidente o‘zim bo‘laman. Nikolinka ham ming sho‘x bo‘lmasin (bola albatta sho‘x bo‘ladi-yu), harqalay, peterburglik yoshlarday bo‘lmaydi [Tolstoy “Urush va tinchlik”, I, II kitoblar: 67].

The pragmatic meaning of promising is given in French:

Mon cher, vous m’avez promis, - обратилась она опять к сыну, прикосновением руки возбуждая его [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 46].

The Uzbek translation:

U yana qo'l tekkizishi bilan o'g'lining g'ashiga tegib:

Do'stim, menga so'z bergansan, - dedi [Tolstoy "Urush va tinchlik", I, II kitoblar: 78]. In the original text, the mother addresses her son as "you," while the translation uses the word "you gave." We see that the translation changes the structure of the original text, i.e., the mother's actions are described first, followed by her speech.

The interrogative sentence in the next passage indicates that a lot of time has passed:

- Bonjour, ma cousine, - сказал Пьер. - Vous ne me reconnaissez pas? [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 49]. We know that the word *cousine* means son or daughter of aunt or uncle. In translation version it is replaced by the word "singlim":

Salom, singlim, - dedi Pyer. - Meni tanimayapsizmi? [Tolstoy "Urush va tinchlik", I, II kitoblar: 84].

Russian literary texts prove that in the 18th and 19th centuries, the names, nicknames, and various positions and titles of nobles were pronounced in French:

Генерал-аншеф князь Николай Андреевич, по прозванию в обществе le roi de Prusse, - с того времени, как при Павле был сослан в деревню и жил безвыездно в своих Лысых Горах с дочерью княжной Марьей, и при ней компаньонкой, m-lle Bourienne [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 81]. In this context they are: "le roi de Prusse" and "m-lle Bourienne".

Let's give one more example:

На днях у Анраксиных я слышала, как одна дама спрашивает: «C'est ça le fameux prince André?» Ma parole d'honneur! - Она засмеялась. - Он так везде принят [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 24].

In anthropocentric linguistics, language units expressing a person's marital status are of particular importance [Nasrullayeva 2018: 199]. In the 18th century, children in Russian noble families usually addressed their parents using French words:

Mon père, André? – сказала неграциозная, неловкая княжна с такой невыразимой прелестью печали и самозабвения, что отец не выдержал ее взгляда и, всхлинув, отвернулся [Толстой «Война и мир», т.2: 26]. From this context, it became clear that the girl addressed her father as "My father, Andre!" So, this kind of address to the father was a communicative norm typical of Russian nobles. It was a kind of fashion and a sign of prosperity. The French address was preserved in noble families for two centuries and was taught to young children.

Indeed, it was customary for children to address their parents in French:

- Прочтите хоть это, mon père, - отвечала княжна, краснея еще более и подавая ему письмо [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 83].

In the Russian aristocratic community, friends and acquaintances also addressed each other in French. Since friends and acquaintances were from noble society, they spoke French freely. The French address, along with expressing special respect, added to the speech and attracted the attention of those around them:

Ma bonne amie, - сказала маленькая княгиня утром 19 марта после завтрака, и губка ее с усиками поднялась по старой привычке [Толстой «Война и мир», т.2: 27]. The indicated phrase means "dear friend." This sentence clearly shows the elegance and nobility of the phrase.

L.N. Tolstoy's characters in his works skillfully use Russian and French words in one sentence. Such bilingualism gives their speech a special beauty and charm:

Тут князь Ипполит задумался, видимо с трудом соображая.

- Она сказала ... да, она сказала: «Девушка, надень livrée (livrée, yani kiyib ol) и поедем со мной, faire des visites» [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 20].

In past centuries, it was common for Russian nobles to greet each other in French and use polite words:

- *Avant tout dites-moi, comment vous allez, chère amie?* Успокойте меня, - сказал он, не изменяя голоса и тоном, в котором из-за приличия и участия просвечивало равнодушие и даже насмешка [Толстой «Война и мир», т.1: 4]. It is known that the character is asking about the general well-being of the communicator. A translator specific to Uzbek linguistic culture translated this sentence as follows:

Avval ayting, azim, salomatligingiz qalay? Meni xotirjam qiling, - dedi knyaz ovozini o'zgartirmasdan, ammo uning odob va mehribonlik uchun aytgan so'zlarida beparvolik va hattoki istehzo ohangi borligi bilinib turar edi [Tolstoy "Urush va tinchlik", I, II kitoblar: 5].

In Russian literary texts French speech formulas and replicas are often used: *Медведя-то, говорит, как не бояться? Да как увидишь его, и страх прошел, как бы только не ушел! Ну, так-то и я. Demain, mon cher!* [Толстой «Война и мир», т.2: 18]. This speech formula is used to say goodbye and means "Goodbye, my dear!" In the quoted passage, although the character is speaking in Russian, he suddenly says goodbye in French. So, French phrases are used more often at the beginning and end of the speech. Such a farewell, on the one hand, attracts people's attention, and on the other hand, it indicates that the speaker is a white man.

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